

ABOUT

This **Communication Toolkit** guides food value chain actors in creating value through transparency. The **Awareness** section shows how embedding transparency in Business Models benefits stakeholders. The **Action** section offers practical interventions to support value creation. The **Aspiration** section encourages scaling transparency innovations socially, organizationally, and institutionally.

AWARENESS

01

Being transparent involves sharing timely, clear information and **being open to dialogue**. It is a **dynamic process** that encourages negotiation and interpretation, creating value and unintended consequences.

Values generated by transparency

Unintended consequences

ACTION

02

Based on the co-creation workshops, **three intervention Scenarios** have been designed to help actors build transparency practices and achieve their goals. Each intervention is supported by a **digital tool** made for the Scenario's needs.

SCENARIO A

Trust Building among Short Food Value Chain Actors

FOCUS
Strengthening connections between actors in the short value chain

CHALLENGE ADDRESSED
Lack of visibility and direct relationships between producers and other actors

DIGITAL TOOL
A lean, standardised, and user-friendly digital representation of local farms, improving visibility and building trust among farmers, retailers, and consumers

SCENARIO B

Collective Branding for Large Food Manufacturing Firms

FOCUS
Creating shared visibility and a coordinated, unified story across the ecosystem

CHALLENGE ADDRESSED
Fragmented messaging and inability to address sector-wide issues collectively

DIGITAL TOOL
A data platform with an incorporated AI Agent to synthesise credible information into a cohesive story

SCENARIO C

Empowerment of Small Food Producers

FOCUS
Targeted support for less-advantaged actors within the value chain

CHALLENGE ADDRESSED
Resource constraints, limited capacity, and barriers to participation in transparency initiatives

DIGITAL TOOL
A digital tool allowing the collection, management and analysis of the necessary data to strengthen production, organisational, and communication capacities

ASPIRATION

03

Transparency in agri-food systems is not only about individual operations becoming more visible. Its full potential is realised when individual actions **connect, aggregate, and contribute to broader systemic change** across the institutional, intraregional, and international levels.

Deepening and extending the intervention

The three Scenarios are interconnected pathways in a **dynamic ecosystem**, where engagement in one may enable entry into the next.

Going beyond Scenarios

Collective action beyond proposed Scenarios, where actors collaborate for shared goals, is vital for **systemic change** and sustainable consumer behavior. Activities on three levels (Business-to-Customer, Business-to-Business, Business-to-Government) serve as an aspirational guideline.

